

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B483
 Date: 03 NOV 2009
 Take Off: 08:30:00Z Z Z
 Landing: 13:09:14Z Z Z
 Flight Time: 4h 39m 14s h m s h m s

Campaign: T-NAWDEX
Operating Area: South West Approaches

POB Position	Name	Institute
1 Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2 Co	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight
3 CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4 CCM training	Robbie Voden	Directflight
5 Mission Scientist	Jon Methven	FAAM
6 Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
7 Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
8 Cloud physics training	Angela Dean	FAAM
9 Core chemistry	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM
10 Mission 2	Andreas Schaefer	Reading
11 Mission 3	Jeffrey Chagnon	Reading
12 Mission 4	Tom Frame	Reading
13 AVAPS	Steve Devereau	
14		
15		
16		
17		
18		
19		

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 1200 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flighter log
	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
Y	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
	Screengrabs
	Planning charts or plots
Y	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2009-11-04	Alan Woolley	Initial version
r1			
r2			

Flight Brief: BAe146 flight B483

Prepared by John Methven, 2 November 2009

Date: Tuesday 3/11/09

Crew list: mission scientist: John Methven
Mission 2: Tom Frame, Andreas Schaefer, Jeffrey Chagnon

Location: Cambridge airport to Southwest Approaches and return.

Aim: Sample the cold front of a developing frontal wave with two dropsonde sections and in situ flying. The second section is further west. Given the rapid eastward flow, this will give a greater separation (in time following the air) between the dropsonde curtains.

Meteorological and other considerations:

The frontal wave is forecast to develop fast and be propagating rapidly towards ESE. The early take-off is necessary get to the south side of the cold front while it is still within the NOTAM A area. In the high resolution Met Office forecasts there is a line of convection with east-west orientation embedded on the northern flank of the front (below the southern end of a tropopause fold). This line will move southwards slowly from ~51N at 09UT, crossing Cornwall by midday. The low level front itself will be south of this. It is expected that there will be strong variation along the front with sections of heavy precipitation and some with none. The latest Met Office forecast also indicates a developing mesocyclone crossing Lands End at about 11. Likely to be an uncertain feature but would be a focus of interest if identified during flight. Towards the end of the flight we aim to take measurements of turbulent humidity and temperature fluxes in the marine boundary layer in strong winds (15-20 m/s) along the English Channel.

Instrument requirements

12 dropsondes, although we may drop fewer.

O3 and TECO NOx to be operated continuously.

Key instruments are those for temperature and water vapour, liquid and ice.

Sortie Details

Flight B483

Tuesday 3 November 2009

0530 Briefing

0830 Take-off

- T+0 Take-off heading for southern edge of NOTAM A at 4W. Fly at fuel efficient altitude, then climbing to highest feasible altitude at way point.
- T+45 Head towards 52N, 6W on level run dropping sondes regularly (5-6 sondes).
- T+75 Head towards SW along edge of NOTAM A on level run.
- T+95 Head S along western edge of NOTAM A on level run, dropping sondes regularly (~5 sondes). Note location of frontal and associated weather for return in situ legs.
- T+115 Reciprocal turn and profile descent to level of interest (5 mins), crossing through rainfall and convection on front on 15 min level run. Location determined from dropsondes and email from ground cf RADAR imagery.
- T+135 Reciprocal turn and profile descent to lower level for 15 min level run.
- T+155 Reciprocal turn and profile descent to minimum safe altitude (preferably within marine boundary layer) for 15 min run.
- T+175 Head towards home along Channel at MSA for further 15 minutes.
- T+190 Profile ascent to level of interest (~FL120) to return to Cambridge.
- T+250 Landing in Cambridge.

1240 Local time – landing

1300 Debrief immediately

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B483

Date:

Project:

Location:

Start End

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	-----	
082552		taxy	0.73 kft	140	
082719		asp	0.72 kft	048	open
083000		T/O	0.71 kft	228	from Cambridge
091111		heim/bbr	20.0 kft	245	open
092114	092642	Profile 1	20.1 - 26.0 kft	243	
092654	093259	Run 1.1	26.0 kft	244	
093958	094014	Run 1.1	26.0 kft	192	real end
094200		Sonde 1	26.0 kft	340	run 1.2 start
094208	101029	Run 1.2	26.1 - 26.0 kft	339	
094705		Sonde 2	26.0 kft	328	
095211		Sonde 3	26.0 kft	328	
095703		Sonde 4	26.0 kft	326	
100344		Sonde 5	26.0 kft	324	
101008		Sonde 6	26.0 kft	324	
101213	103326	Run 1.3	26.1 - 26.0 kft	254	
103321		Sonde 7	26.0 kft	252	
103331	105752	Run 1.4	26.0 kft	252	
103915		Sonde 8	26.0 kft	202	
104520		Sonde 9	26.0 kft	203	
105113		Sonde 10	26.0 kft	198	
105718		Sonde 11	26.0 kft	351	
105752	111536	Profile 2	26.0 - 8.0 kft	347	
111728	113931	Run 2.1	8.0 kft	181	
114115	114805	Profile 3	8.0 - 1.7 kft	342	
114816	120310	Run 3.1	1.7 kft	346	
120310	120437	Profile 4	1.7 - 0.86 kft	041	
120437	121136	Profile 5	0.86 - 8.0 kft	040	
121136	124322	Run 4.1	8.0 kft	036	
124440	125752	Run 5.1	10.0 - 9.9 kft	074	
130914		Land	0.83 kft	232	cambridge

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 3/1/09

Flight No: B483

 Pre-Flighter: *Am*

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect spanners	Core Chem - 9/16" & 11/16"
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	<i>OFF A/C</i>
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom C	Checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
24	<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	<i>N/A</i>
25	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	<i>N/A</i>
26	<input type="checkbox"/>	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	<i>IN COCKPIT NOW AT DAY</i>
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	<i>N/A</i>
28	<input type="checkbox"/>	3876 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	<i>N/A</i>

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
29	<input type="checkbox"/>	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	<i>N/A</i>
30	<input type="checkbox"/>	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	<i>"</i>
31	<input type="checkbox"/>	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	<i>"</i>
32	<input type="checkbox"/>	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	<i>"</i>
33	<input type="checkbox"/>	3786 CPC	Drained	<i>"</i>
34	<input type="checkbox"/>	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	<i>"</i>
<u>External Checks</u>				
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	<i>TWC COVERED WITH BUN BAG LIME</i>
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	<i>REMOVED PREVIOUSLY WITH TWC COVER</i>
<i>NO COVERS FITTED EXCEPT CONDENSERS. ALL IN HOLD!!</i>				
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
47	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
48	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
49	<input type="checkbox"/>			
50	<input type="checkbox"/>			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
51	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
52	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
53	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

Flight:

B483

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson-Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Radiometers

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

ADA:

CCN:

CDP (Fuselage)

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI Inlet:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS)

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B483
Date: 03 Nov 09

Instruments

1. MPDS worked for first 20 minutes. Then fell over Error 772
2. ISDN error 678 following MPDS fall-over
3. Satcom handset dialtone ok
4. Nevz TWC u/s all flight. No covers were put in place overnight.

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B483	Date	03/11/2009	Operator	Steve Devereau	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
09:42:03	1	Launch	359.00 -30.30 55.19 281.30 55.80 0.60 -5.248900 49.499800 7940.80 0 55.19 55.19 0 0.00 7945.30
09:51:32	1	splash	989.64 13.51 88.33 246.16 18.24 -11.16 -4.967933 49.474848 59.23 9 88.33 89.81 9 2.56 103.04
	1		Good drop
09:47:06	2	Launch	359.40 -30.20 50.95 278.50 59.20 0.70 -5.374900 49.860100 7934.60 0 50.95 50.95 0 0.00 7914.40
09:56:47	2	splash	989.73 13.36 90.17 244.28 18.36 -9.03 -5.078888 49.836367 67.56 6 90.17 91.43 6 3.33 74.05
	2		Good drop
09:52:09	3	Launch	359.40 -30.00 46.10 278.40 62.60 0.90 -5.499200 50.213000 7933.30 0 46.10 46.10 0 0.00 7889.40
10:01:39	3	Land	971.63 12.16 97.02 239.23 16.47 -11.19 -5.190810 50.194104 230.95 6 97.02 98.16 6 3.35 218.31
	3		Good drop
09:57:06	4	Launch	359.60 -29.70 42.15 274.00 64.80 1.30 -5.621300 50.553900 7930.80 0 42.15 42.15 0 0.00 7863.20
10:07:05	4	Land	989.71 12.30 83.83 282.90 10.49 -9.39 -5.291322 50.536808 92.16 9 83.83 83.55 9 2.74 63.99
	4		Good drop
10:03:33	5	Launch	359.70 -29.90 21.14 274.50 66.80 0.90 -5.786300 51.009200 7927.20 0 21.14 21.14 0 0.00 7821.80
10:13:01	5	Land	987.67 13.28 69.39 275.22 15.20 -9.70 -5.455024 50.995048 137.50 9 69.39 69.33 9 2.56 68.67
	5		Good drop
10:10:06	6	Launch	359.50 -29.70 6.96 273.00 65.60 1.00 -5.952800 51.451700 7932.10 0 6.96 6.96 0 0.00 7787.30
10:19:16	6	Land	986.51 12.83 65.14 282.75 14.91 -10.71 -5.659056 51.442313 177.20 7 65.14 64.68 7 3.08 62.60
	6		Good drop
10:33:21	7	Launch	359.30 -30.20 15.76 269.10 64.80 0.60 -7.747200 51.024500 7935.80 0 15.76 15.76 0 0.00 7809.60
10:42:43	7	Land	988.81 12.35 60.70 283.74 15.61 -10.91 -7.453968 51.013228 152.66 7 60.70 60.46 7 3.52 74.67

	7		Good drop
10:39:18	8	Launch	359.50 -30.10 35.97 272.10 62.00 1.00 -7.831400 50.574500 7932.80 0 35.97 35.97 0 0.00 7841.20
10:48:38	8	Land	990.96 12.70 58.68 290.42 15.51 -11.90 -7.510357 50.572371 117.86 6 58.68 57.29 6 3.61 69.15
	8		Good drop
10:45:15	9		359.60 -29.80 42.55 273.90 58.00 0.40 -7.833200 50.077000 7929.70 0 42.55 42.55 0 0.00 7877.00
10:54:35	9		989.39 11.94 78.31 286.71 13.11 -10.98 -7.518471 50.072403 98.47 6 78.31 79.82 6 2.71 91.96
10:51:15	10		359.40 -29.50 38.10 275.70 51.20 1.10 -7.829300 49.565000 7933.30 0 38.10 38.10 0 0.00 7920.60
11:00:42	10		993.42 11.39 92.79 286.96 19.55 -10.99 -7.539491 49.554496 37.08 6 92.79 93.14 6 4.86 78.31
	10		Good drop
10:57:21	11		359.20 -29.60 53.77 280.10 58.60 1.20 -7.518600 49.242400 7936.70 0 53.77 53.77 0 0.00 7940.00
11:06:51	11		9999.00 99.00 999.00 270.66 12.91 -11.64 -7.234457 49.231446 99999.00 9 999.00 999.00 9 2.22 64.79
	11		Good drop

South West England: latest radar

Digital Map Data:

© Collins Bartholomew Ltd (2006)

Postcode information:

© Royal Mail Group PLC (2006)

Weather warnings overview

Severe weather warnings have been issued for South West England

Click on a map to see all warnings issued for South West England.

Latest observations - 0900 on 3 Nov 09: South West England

Location	Weather	Temp	Wind			Vis	Pressure / trend
			Dir	Speed	Gust		
Boscombe Down		11.7 °C	SW	13 mph		25 km	990 hPa, Falling
Bristol Filton		13.1 °C	WSW	18 mph		21 km	988 hPa, Falling
Camborne		13.4 °C	WSW	24 mph	41 mph	8 km	992 hPa, Falling
Cardinham		12.0 °C	WSW	26 mph	40 mph	7 km	990 hPa, Falling
Chivenor		13.0 °C	W	22 mph	44 mph	11 km	989 hPa, Falling
Culdrose		13.4 °C	W	21 mph	44 mph	8 km	993 hPa, Falling
Dunkeswell		11.3 °C	WSW	15 mph		15 km	990 hPa, Falling
Hurn		13.5 °C	W	14 mph		30 km	991 hPa, Falling
Isle of Portland		13.5 °C	W	26 mph	44 mph	13 km	991 hPa, Falling
Larkhill		11.8 °C	SW	9 mph		25 km	989 hPa, Falling
Liscombe		10.7 °C	W	16 mph	39 mph	10 km	989 hPa, Falling
Little Rissington		10.7 °C	SW	15 mph		7 km	987 hPa, Falling
Lyneham		11.6 °C	SW	9 mph		15 km	989 hPa, Falling
Plymouth		13.1 °C	WSW	24 mph	36 mph	6 km	991 hPa, Falling
St Mary's		14.0 °C	SW	30 mph	45 mph	6 km	993 hPa, Falling
Yeovilton		13.1 °C	SW	7 mph		12 km	990 hPa, Falling

Observations are subject to final quality control after publication on this web site.

[More UK observations](#)

24 hours ending 2100 on 2 Nov 09: South West England

Highest max	13.5 °C	Isles Of Scilly
Lowest max	8.9 °C	Liscombe
Lowest min	3.1 °C	Little Rissington
Highest rainfall	15.2 mm	Cardinham
Sunniest	5.1 hours	Hurn

During snow events, rainfall amounts are subject to error until final quality control is done.

Last updated: 0023 on Tue 3 Nov 2009

UK last month**September 2009**

Mean temperatures were generally above the 1971-2000 normal for September, ranging from about 0.3 °C above average in Wales and south-west England to about 1.5 °C above in northern Scotland. Rainfall was well below average across most of the UK, the main exception being parts of north-east Scotland. It was very dry across much of East Anglia, the Midlands, south Wales and Northern Ireland with less than a third of the normal amount. Provisionally, it was the driest September across England since 1997 and the 11th driest in a series from 1914. Sunshine was generally close to normal. The sunniest places were in southern England and south Wales, where totals were typically 20% above average, and the dullest were in north-west Scotland where they were about 20% below.

A maximum temperature of 28.7 °C was recorded at Gravesend (Kent) on the 8th. A minimum temperature of -1.2 °C was recorded at Kinbrace (Highland) on the 19th. A site near Fochabers (Moray) recorded 123.6 mm of rainfall in the 24 hours ending at 0900 on the 4th.

[Monthly assessment](#) | [Actual and anomaly maps](#) | [Regional values](#)

Analysis chart valid 18 UTC TUE 03 NOV 2009

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